

COMPARISON OF CRYSTALLIZED PHENOL APPLICATION AND MODIFIED LIMBERG FLAP TECHNIQUE IN THE TREATMENT OF PILONIDAL SINUS

Keywords

Pilonidal sinüs,

Modified limberg flap,

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Mustafa Uğur¹

ABSTRACT

Crystallized phenol application and the modified Limberg flap technique are commonly used methods in the treatment of pilonidal sinus. This study aims to compare the outcomes of these two techniques and identify their advantages and disadvantages. The medical records of patients who underwent crystallized phenol application and modified Limberg flap surgery between 2019 and 2024 were reviewed retrospectively. The two groups were compared in terms of age, gender, body mass index, surgical site infections, drain usage, and recurrence rates. The study revealed that crystallized phenol was applied to 44 patients, while 56 patients underwent the modified Limberg flap procedure. In the crystallized phenol group, all procedures were performed under local anesthesia, whereas the patients in the Limberg flap group underwent surgery under spinal anesthesia. There were no significant differences between the groups regarding age, gender, and body mass index ($p>0.05$). Patients treated with phenol were discharged on the same day, while the average hospital stay for the flap group was 1.2 ± 0.5 days. In terms of recurrence, it was found to be 20.5% in the crystallized phenol group and 1.8% in the modified flap group, with the difference between the groups being statistically significant ($p<0.05$). The main advantages of crystallized phenol application were its ability to be performed under local anesthesia and not requiring hospitalization, while its primary disadvantage was the high recurrence rate. In contrast, the main advantage of the modified Limberg flap method was its low recurrence rate.

INTRODUCTION

Sacrococcygeal pilonidal sinus (PS) disease is a condition caused by the penetration of fallen hairs into the natal cleft. The disease is observed in young males at twice the rate compared to females. Its incidence is determined to be 26/100,000.^{1,2}

The main treatment methods for this condition involve sinus excision, primary repair, or various flap techniques aimed at shifting the midline. Despite the use of multiple treatment methods, there is still no consensus on which one is ideal. The main reason for this is the recurrence observed at varying rates after treatment.³⁻⁶

One of the commonly used flap techniques is the Limberg flap method. In this technique, after a rhomboid excision is performed to remove the pilonidal sinuses, the resulting defect is closed using a flap described by Limberg. The method was modified in 2004 by Menteş and colleagues. In this modification, the lower edge of the incision was shifted laterally to reduce the inferomedial recurrence seen in the classical Limberg flap technique. This modification has been reported to result in lower recurrence rates.^{7,8}

The treatment of PS disease with liquid phenol was first described by Maurice in 1964. Later, treatment with crystallized phenol was introduced. The main advantages of this method include its ability to be performed under local anesthesia, quick return to work, and low recurrence rates.^{9,10}

In this study, the results of patients treated with the modified Limberg flap method and those treated with crystallized phenol were compared.

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

Approval for this study was obtained from the Chief Physician's Office of Hatay Mustafa Kemal University, Tayfur Sökmen Faculty of Medicine Training and Research Hospital. The medical records of patients treated with a modified Limberg flap and crystallized phenol for pilonidal sinus between July 2019 and July 2024 were retrospectively reviewed. Patients who did not attend regular follow-ups, had incomplete records, had recurrent pilonidal sinus, or received treatments other than crystallized phenol and modified Limberg flap were excluded from the study. The patients included in the study were evaluated in terms of age, gender, body mass index (BMI), treatment method, hospital stay, drain usage, drain removal time, postoperative bleeding, wound infection, wound dehiscence, and recurrence development, and the treatment methods were compared. All patients were informed about the disease and treatment options. The choice of treatment method was based on patient preference, the number of sinuses, and the distance of the sinuses from the midline. Crystallized phenol treatment was not recommended for patients with more than five sinuses or sinuses located more than 3 cm away from the midline.

Surgical Method

One hour before the procedure, all patients were administered 1 gram of intravenous cefazolin sodium for prophylactic antibiotic therapy.

Crystallized Phenol Method

This method was applied as previously described by Dođru and colleagues¹⁰. The patients' sacrococcygeal area was prepared by using depilatory creams to remove hair prior to the operation. Just before the procedure, local anesthesia containing lidocaine was administered to all patients, and the procedure was performed in the prone position. A mini excision was made to include the sinus openings, and the contents and hairs of the sinus were completely removed. After applying vaseline around the sinus, crystallized phenol was applied into the sinus. The procedure was repeated 2-3 times for all sinuses, followed by dressing, and the patients were discharged on the same day.

Modified Limberg Flap Method

This method was applied as previously described by Menteş and colleagues⁷. The sacrococcygeal area of all patients was

prepared by using depilatory creams for hair removal before the operation. One hour before surgery, 1 gram of intravenous cefazolin sodium was administered. All patients received spinal anesthesia, and the procedure was performed in the prone position. A rhomboid-shaped incision was made to include all sinuses, and excision was performed to involve the postsacral fascia. Special care was taken to ensure the lower edge of the rhomboid shape was 1-2 cm lateral to the midline. To close the rhomboid defect, a fasciocutaneous transposition flap containing the gluteal fascia was prepared and rotated to cover the defect. A vacuum drain was placed over the postsacral fascia, and the wound was closed with absorbable polyglycatin sutures in the subcutaneous tissue. The skin was closed with polypropylene sutures. All patients were admitted to the postoperative service, and the drain was removed when the drainage fluid reached 25 cc.

Statistical Analysis

The data analysis was performed using the SPSS 21.0 software package. Descriptive statistics included the percentage distribution (column percentage) for categorical variables, and the mean and standard deviations for continuous variables. To examine the relationship between categorical variables and the dependent variable, Pearson's chi-square test, Yates-corrected chi-square test, and Fisher's exact test were used. The Shapiro-Wilk test was used to assess the normality of continuous variables. Since the continuous variables did not follow a normal distribution, the Mann-Whitney U test was used to compare two continuous variables, and a p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

In this study, the medical records of 120 patients treated with crystallized phenol and the modified Limberg flap were retrospectively reviewed. The records of 20 patients who had incomplete data or did not attend follow-ups were excluded from the study. The mean age of all patients was 24.3 ± 5.73 years, with no significant difference between the groups ($p > 0.05$) (Table 1). In the phenol group, 35 patients were male and 9 were female, while in the Limberg flap group, there were 46 males and 10 females, and there were no significant differences between the groups regarding gender ($p > 0.05$) (Table 1). There was no significant difference between the groups in terms of body mass index ($p > 0.05$) (Table 1). The average drain removal time was 2.5 ± 1.9 days. The number of sinuses and the hospital stay were significantly

Table 1. Comparison of Demographic Data, Number of Sinuses, and Length of Hospital Stay by Group

	Total	Phenol	Limberg Flap	p
	Mean±SD	Mean±SD	Mean±SD	
Age	24,3±5,73	23,4±4,6	24,9±6,4	0,111*
Sinus Number	3,26±1,7	2,0±0,9	4,2±1,6	<0,001*
Hospital Stay (Days)	0,7±0,7	0,1±0,2	1,2±0,5	<0,001*
BMI	25,5±2,1	25,5±2,4	25,5±1,9	0,921*
Gender	Number-Percentage	Number-Percentage	Number-Percentage	
Male	81-%81	35-%79,5	46-%82,1	0,943**
Female	19-%19	9-%20,5	10-%17,9	

SD: Standard Deviation, *Mann Whitney U Testi, ** Yates Corrected Chi-Square Test

Table 2. Complications According to the Method

		Total		Phenol		Limberg Flap		
		Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	
Complication	Absent	73	73,0	29	65,9	44	78,6	0,234
	Present	27	27,0	15	34,1	12	21,4	
Recurrence	Absent	90	90,0	35	79,5	55	98,2	0,004**
	Present	10	10,0	9	20,5	1	1,8	
Wound Infection	Absent	92	92,0	40	90,9	52	92,9	0,728**
	Present	8	8,0	4	9,1	4	7,1	
Wound Dehiscence	Absent	93	93,0	44	100,0	49	87,5	
	Present	7	7,0	0	0,0	7	12,5	
Bleeding	Absent	98	98,0	42	95,5	56	100,0	
	Present	2	2,0	2	4,5	0	0,0	

*Yates Corrected Chi-Square, **Fisher's Exact Test

higher in the Limberg flap group ($p < 0.05$) (Table 2). There was no significant difference between the groups in terms of surgical site infection ($p > 0.05$) (Table 2). When evaluating recurrence, 9 patients (20.5%) in the phenol group experienced recurrence, while only 1 patient (1.8%) in the Limberg flap group experienced recurrence. The difference between the groups was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) (Table 2).

DISCUSSION

Pilonidal sinus disease is a condition that is more commonly seen in young men and negatively affects quality of life. Several surgical methods are used in treatment, based on excision followed by primary repair or closure of the defect with various flaps. These methods can lead to various surgical complications, such as wound infections, seromas, and bleeding, at varying rates. An important issue in the treatment of pilonidal sinus disease is recurrence, which occurs at different rates depending on the method used. Additionally, prolonged hospital stays, drain use, and delays in returning to work lead to various economic losses.^{11,12} For these reasons, efforts have been made to find an ideal treatment method that requires minimal hospital stay, has low costs, and a lower complication rate. To this end, liquid phenol was first used in the treatment of pilonidal sinus by Maurice and Greenwood. Phenol is an acidic hydrocarbon. It exists in crystal form at room temperature and turns into a liquid at body temperature. After initial use of liquid phenol, recurrence rates as high as 27% were observed. However, later studies showed that crystallized phenol, when applied after widening the sinus opening and clearing the sinus content, resulted in successful treatment, did not require hospitalization, and reduced recurrence rates to as low as 1%. Other complications observed after phenol application include wound infections, abscesses, and burns on healthy skin.^{9,10,13,14}

One of the most commonly used surgical methods in the treatment of sacrococcygeal pilonidal sinus disease is the Limberg flap technique. The technique has been modified by shifting the lower edge of the rhomboid excision 1-2 cm laterally from the midline. The main advantage of this method is its low recurrence rate, which ranges from 0% to 8.3%. Seroma, bleeding, and wound infections are noted as other complications.^{7,15,16,17}

In our study, the results of patients treated with crystallized phenol were compared with those of patients treated with the modified Limberg flap technique. While patients treated with

crystallized phenol were discharged on the same day, patients treated with the modified Limberg flap technique had an average hospital stay of 1.2 ± 0.5 days. Since the study was retrospective, return-to-work time was not available. There was no significant difference between the groups in terms of wound infection.

Despite being applied to patients with fewer sinuses, and the procedure being repeated up to 3 times in case of recurrence, the recurrence rate in the crystallized phenol group was found to be high at 20.5%. In contrast, the recurrence rate in the modified Limberg flap group was found to be 1.8%. A detailed review of the patient files revealed that 17 out of the 20 patients excluded from the study for not attending follow-up were in the crystallized phenol group. It was hypothesized that patients who had resolved symptoms may have a tendency not to return for follow-up. This could be a reason for the higher recurrence rate in the crystallized phenol group.

CONCLUSION

The main advantage of the modified Limberg flap technique in the treatment of sacrococcygeal pilonidal sinus disease is its low recurrence rate. The use of spinal anesthesia, longer hospital stay, and the requirement for drain placement are the main disadvantages of this technique compared to the crystallized phenol group. The most significant advantages of crystallized phenol application are that it can be performed under local anesthesia and that patients can be discharged on the same day. However, its high recurrence rate stands out as its most important disadvantage. We believe that patients to whom crystallized phenol will be applied should be given detailed information about the recurrence rates prior to the procedure.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest related to this study.

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No

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